

ANALYSIS OF ZAKAT WORTHY VILLAGE THROUGH ZAKAT VILLAGE INDEX MEASUREMENT

Erwanda Nuryahya¹, Aas Nurasyiah¹, Sri Yuyu Ninglasari¹

¹Indonesia University of Education

erwandanuryahya@student.upi.edu, asnur.fna@upi.edu, sriyayu3@student.upi.edu

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to identify zakat-worthy villages through the Index of Zakat Villages. This model is used to measure the condition of a village whether it is feasible to be assisted or not by the zakat funds. The supporting dimension of the Zakat Village Index consists of five dimensions, namely economic, health, education, humanity, and da'wah. Then the dimensions are reduced again to fifteen variables and 39 indicators. The more IDZ values approach one, the more the village is not prioritized to be assisted. Conversely, the more IDZ approaches zero, the village will be prioritized for assistance. The subject of this research is in Cipancar village, Serangpanjang sub-district, Subang district. The results indicates that out of the 5 dimensions of IDZ tested in Cipancar village, Serangpanjang sub-district, Subang district was included in the Zakat Village Index. In which the average of economic dimension score is 0.07, health dimension is 0.05, education dimension is 0.13, humanity dimension is 0.12, and dimension of da'wah is 0.14. The total IDZ value is 0.51. Based on the results of these tests it can be concluded that the Cipancar village in the lengthy district can be considered for assistance through zakat funds.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2538881

1. Introduction

Zakat in Indonesia has experienced a very significant increase both in terms of collection and distribution of zakat funds. This was conveyed by Irfan Syauqi Beik that the development of zakat in Indonesia has undergone a better change especially after the issuance of Act No. 23 Year 2011 which concentrated on collecting and distributing zakat funds through the National Board of Zakat (BAZNAS) to manage zakat in Indonesia nationally. With the regulation governing zakat management in Indonesia, it has impacted the growth of zakat funds collected and distributed in Indonesia (BAZNAS Center of Strategic Studies, 2018).

The effectiveness of the distribution of zakat funds needs to be increased because there are still many people in Indonesia classified as poor. Based on data from the Central Bureau of Statistics (2017) the number of poor people (population with per capita expenditure per month below the poverty line) in Indonesia in September 2016 reached 27.76 million people (10.76%). Even out of a total of 34, three provinces on the island of Java themselves entered the order of the three largest number of poor people in Indonesia. West Java Province itself ranks third after the provinces of East Java and Central Java with nearly 3.8 million people.

Whereas the biggest zakat fund potential is located in the province of West Java. Here are three provinces with the largest potential zakat funds:

TABLE 1. ZAKAT POTENTIAL BY PROVINCE

Region	Potential of Zakat (in trillions rupiah)
West Java	17.67
East Java	15.5
Central Java	13.28

Source : Mukhlis & Beik (2013)

Subang is one of the poorest districts in West Java, where the total poor population in subang reaches 700 thousand people, equivalent to 40% of the total population in the Subang which reaches 1.6 million people (Tempo.co, 2016). Whereas Subang has great industrial potential in West Java (Budiman, 2017).

In the distribution of zakat funds, BAZNAS as the national zakat management board has various programs. One of the program is zakat community development (community / village-based zakat program). Zakat community development is a community development program by integrating social aspects (education, religion, environment, and other social aspects) and comprehensive economic aspects which zakat, infaq, and alms are the main funding sources expected through this program to be created prosperous and independent community (Mintarti, 2016).

A village has the right to receive zakat community development program if the village is indicated to be worthy of zakat through the measurement of the zakat village index. Zakat village index is an instrument issued by BAZNAS as a measuring instrument for a village entitled to receive zakat assistance. Zakat village index is made in order to make the zakat community development program effective and right on target (BAZNAS Center of Strategic Studies, 2017). However, there are still few resources available to conduct research on villages that are eligible to receive zakat, resulting in that there are still at least indicated villages entitled to receive zakat funds.

Research on zakat-worthy villages is still little discussed when compared with studies on the human development index (IPM) or the village development index. There have been several previous studies that reviewed the human development index, including those conducted by Maniyalath & Narendran (2016); Aydin (2017); Ramani (2014); Lumbantoruan & Hidayat (2016). In these studies revealed that the human development index has an influence on aspects of human life. While the research of the zakat village index itself is still very difficult to find. However, there are studies conducted by Riyanto & Junaedi (2017); Setyobakti (2017) measures a village using the develop village index. From the study explained that the develop village index was used to measure the extent to which a village could develop.

From this phenomenon researchers are interested in researching the index of zakat-worthy villages through the measurement of the zakat village index. The village that was used as the object of research was in Cipancar village, Serangpanjang Sub-district, West Java Subang District. The results of this study are expected to help the effectiveness of zakat funds through the zakat community development program.

2. Literature Review

Zakat Village Index or abbreviated with IDZ is an indicator that is able to measure (assesment) conditions and situations of a village whether the village is feasible or not to be empowered using zakat funds. Village Index Zakat is also compiled based on process-oriented where IDZ itself will later measure and assess various kinds of village development efforts.

Therefore IDZ itself can be used as a mechanism to measure the welfare of a village and can also be used as a monitoring and evaluation tool for the zakat village program that has been carried out by zakat management institutions (BAZNAS Center of Strategic Studies, 2017)

The constituent components of IDZ consist of five components which are important aspects in life, namely Economy, Health, Education, Social and Humanity, and Da'wah or can be said to be a variable in IDZ research. Of each of the variables that are interconnected, to facilitate the calculation, it is made more specific, namely to become 15 variables. From each indicator, 39 indicators are formed which have their own weight. Calculation estimation techniques to obtain IDZ values using the Multi-Stage Weighted Index method. This method combines each weighting stage in each of the indexing components. So the weighting must be done in stages and procedural (BAZNAS Center of Strategic Studies, 2017).

Previous studies that measured welfare in a village were carried out by Rosni (2017) who measured the level of welfare of fishermen in Desa Dahari Selebar, Talawi District, Batubara Regency, using the BKKBN welfare indicator. Based on the results of the study, it was found that the fishing communities in the village were mostly at the level of welfare of Pre-prosperous Families, as many as 63.63%, this reflected that they had not been able to comply basic needs. The percentage of people who are at least in the welfare level of Family Prosperity II is 4.56%, this reflects that 4.56% of the people of Desa Dahari Selebar are able to meet basic needs and other needs.

Another research that measures population welfare in a village was carried out by Sari, Haryono, & Rosanti (2014) who measured the level of income and welfare of corn farmer households in Muara Putih Village, Merak Batin Village, and Krawang Sari Village, Natar District, South Lampung Regency using the BPS welfare index. The results of the study found that farmers' income from corn and non-maize (on farm) contributed 85.65% more when compared to other operating income (off farm). Whereas according to BPS welfare criteria, corn farmers in the area are in the prosperous category, which is 70.59%.

The next study that measures women's entrepreneurship level in a village is carried out by Maniyalath & Narendran (2016) using the human development index. The results of the study stated that the high and low participation of women to become entrepreneurs was due to their income and their religiosity.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Object of Research

This research was conducted in Cipancar Village, Serang Panjang District, Subang Regency. Consideration in determining the village area based on the location that is easily accessible and the level of ability of researchers to conduct research in the village area. The scope of this research is to describe which villages are more eligible to receive assistance from zakat funds. The population of this study is all residents in Cipancar village, Serang Panjang sub-district, Subang Regency. However, due to the researchers' limitations, the assessment of several indicators did not involve the entire population but the assessment was assessed and validated by local experts and community leaders.

3.2. Data Collection Technique

To obtain relevant information in order to support research, the authors use data collection methods by: 1) library studies, 2) field studies, 3) questionnaires, 4) interviews.

3.3. Data Analysis Method

The data analysis tool used in this study is part of a quantitative method that has its own formula also through several stages of calculation. The following stages of the calculation process of the Zakat Village Index:

1. Each indicator has its own assessment criteria which are measured using a Likert scale which has 5 levels of assessment, where the lowest value starts from number 1 and the largest value is 5. This assessment is obtained from the data collected in relation to village conditions and adjusted to criteria in each indicator. The higher the value obtained by a village, the more the village is not prioritized to be assisted with zakat funds. But on the contrary, if the weight of the village's value is lower then the village is increasingly prioritized for assistance. Then after getting the actual figures (based on facts, findings and data obtained that have been adjusted to the Likert scale criteria) (BAZNAS Center of Strategic Studies, 2017). Here's how to calculate the Zakat Village Index indicator:

$$Indicator_x = \frac{(Score_x - Score_{min})}{(Score_{max} - Score_{min})}$$

Information :

Indicator_x = Score of indicator x

Score_x = Score on indicator x

Score_{max} = 1 (smallest value)

Score_{min} = 5 (biggest value)

2. After the value of each indicator is obtained, then multiplied by the weight of each indicator to get an indicator index.
3. Then the indicator index is grouped according to its dimensions, and multiplied by the weight of each dimension to get the dimension index.
4. The index of each variable is multiplied by the weight of each variable to get a variable index. The result is a composite index which can be referred to as the Zakat Village Index. The formula is as follows:

$$IDZ = (X1ek + X2ks + X3pe + X4ke + X5da)$$

IDZ = Zakat village index

X1,...,X5 = Assessment weight

ek = Economic dimension

ks = Health dimension

pe = Education dimension

ke = Humanity dimension

da = Da'wah Dimension

The Zakat Village Index value ranges between 0 and 1. The closer to 1 the village is not prioritized for assistance. Conversely, the more IDZ approaches 0, the village will be prioritized for assistance. The weight of the assessment itself as can be seen in the table below:

TABLE 2. RANGE SCORE OF ZAKAT INDEX VILLAGE (IDZ)

Range Score	Information	Interpretation
0.00 – 0.20	Not very good	Highly prioritized for assistance
0.21 – 0.40	Not good	Prioritized for assistance
0.41 – 0.60	Good enough	Can be considered for assistance
0.61 – 0.80	Good	Less prioritized for assistance
0.81 – 1.00	Very good	Not prioritized for assistance

4. Results

4.1. General Description of Research Sites

4.1.1. Geographical location

Cipancar Village is located in the Serangpanjang District, Subang Regency, West Java. Cipancar Village consists of 12 citizen associations (RW) that have regional boundaries including:

- ❖ North is bordered by Ponggang Village, Serang Panjang District
- ❖ South of the border with Bandung Regency
- ❖ East is bordered by Cikujang, Kecamatan Serangpanjang
- ❖ West of the border with Pusaka Mulya Village, Purwakarta Regency

Cipancar Village has an area of 796.25 Ha with a population of 5,258 people consisting of 1,703 Family Heads and a population density of 66,034 / km. Topography of Cipancar Village itself is dominated by rice fields with an area of 277 Ha.

4.1.2. Population

Information on Cipancar Village population is obtained from observations. Based on the data obtained, the total population of Desa Cipancar totaled 5,258 people consisting of 2,631 residents who were male and 2,627 women. This means that the number of comparisons between men and women in Cipancar Village is almost balanced. Citizens of Cipancar Village itself are dominated by Sundanese and the entire community is Muslim. The education level of the Cipancar Village community is the majority up to the level of elementary school / equivalent, which is 1,568 people and only about 1.06% are educated above the high school level. This shows that the level of education in Cipancar Village is still relatively low.

4.1.3. Livelihood

The number of productive workforce (ages 18-56 years) in Cipancar Village reached 1,624 people. For the quality of its own workforce, it is dominated by people with an elementary school (SD) background with a total of 1,568 people, while the workforce with a college education background only reaches 56 people.

FIGURE 1. LIVELIHOODS OF RESIDENTS IN CIPANCAR VILLAGE

Source : Cipancar Village Government (2018)

4.2. The results of the Zakat Village Index weighting in Cipancar village, Serang Panjang sub-district, Subang district.

In this section we will discuss the results of weighting IDZ values in Cipancar village, Serang Panjang sub-district, Subang. The division of each of these weights will then bring up the IDZ value which will be explained based on the IDZ variable, the following explanation:

4.2.1. IDZ Characteristics Based on Economic Variables

Based on the results of IDZ's calculations, the economic value of Cipancar Village has a value of 0.28 which means that the economic condition of Cipancar Village is at an unfavorable

level so it is prioritized for assistance. The description of the weighted values of Economic variables based on the results of variable weighting is explained as follows:

Table 3. Total Dimension Weight of Economic Variables in Cipancar Village

Variable	Dimension	Dimension Weight	Dimension Index Value	Information
Economic	Productive Economic Activities	0	0	Not Very Good
	Village Trade Center	0,11	0,47	Good Enough
	Access Transportation and Shipping Logistics Services	0,11	0,50	Good Enough
	Access to Financial Institutions	0,06	0,22	Not Good
IDZ Score of Economic Variable		0,28		Not Good

Source : Data processed by the researcher

This value is influenced by the absence of several variables that support the economic variables in Cipancar Village. Like there is no market as a means of trading and provider of community needs both offline and online. Moreover, the absence of financial institutions both sharia and conventional.

4.2.2. IDZ Characteristic Based on Health Variables

Based on the IDZ calculation results, the value of health variable in Cipancar Village gets a value of 0.32 which means that the economic condition of Cipancar Village is at an unfavorable level so it is prioritized for assistance. The description of the weighted values of Economic variables based on the results of variable weighting is explained as follows:

TABLE 4. TOTAL DIMENSION WEIGHT OF HEALTH VARIABLES IN CIPANCAR VILLAGE

Variable	Dimension	Dimension Weight	Dimension Index Value	Information
Health	Public health	0,10	0,25	Not Good
	Health services	0,16	0,44	Good Enough
	Health Insurance	0,06	0,25	Not Good
IDZ Score of Health Variable		0,32		Not Good

Source : Data processed by the researcher

4.2.3. IDZ Characteristics Based on Education Variables

Based on the calculation of IDZ, the education variable value of Cipancar Village gets a value of 0.64 which shows that the educational condition of Cipancar Village is not prioritized for assistance. Description of variable values Education based on the results of variable weighting is explained as follows:

TABLE 5. TOTAL DIMENSION WEIGHT OF EDUCATION VARIABLES IN CIPANCAR VILLAGE

Variable	Dimension	Dimension Weight	Dimension Index Value	Information
Education	education level and literacy	0,26	0,51	Good enough
	Educational facilities	0,38	0,76	Good
IDZ Score of Education Variable		0,64		Good

Source : Data processed by the researcher

4.2.4. IDZ Characteristics Based on Social and Humanity Variables

Based on the results of IDZ calculations, the value of the Social and Humanity variable in Cipancar Village gets a value of 0.70 which shows that the social and humanitarian conditions of Cipancar Village are at a good level so that the social and humanitarian aspects of Cipancar Village are less prioritized for assistance. The description of Social and Humanity variable values based on the results of variable weighting is explained as follows:

TABLE 6. TOTAL DIMENSION WEIGHT OF SOCIAL AND HUMANITY VARIABLES IN CIPANCAR VILLAGE

Variable	Dimension	Dimension Weight	Dimension Index Value	Information
Social and Humanity	Facility for Open Community Interaction Space	0,24	0,67	Goof
	Electrical, Communication and Information Infrastructure	0,35	0,81	Very Good
	Natural Disaster Mitigation	0,11	0,5	Good Enough
IDZ Score of Social and Humanity Variable		0,70		Good

Source : Data processed by the researcher

4.2.5. IDZ Characteristics Based on Da'wah Variables

Based on the results of IDZ calculations, the Da'wah variable in Cipancar Village gets a value of 0.65 which shows that da'wah activities are at a good level so that aspects of Cipancar Village's religious activities are less prioritized for assistance. The description of the value of Da'wah variables based on the results of variable weighting is explained as follows:

TABLE 7. TOTAL DIMENSION WEIGHT OF DA'WAH VARIABLES IN CIPANCAR VILLAGE

Variable	Dimension	Dimension Weight	Dimension Index Value	Information
Da'wah	Availability of Religious Facilities & Assistance	0,20	0,59	Good Enough
	Level of Community Religion Knowledge	0,27	0,89	Very Good
	Level of Religious Activities and Community Participation	0,18	0,48	Good Enough
IDZ Score of Da'wah Variable		0,65		Good

Source : Data processed by the researcher

4.3. IDZ results and the feasibility of Cipancar village, Serangpanjang sub-district in received zakat assistance

Zakat Village Index aims to identify whether a village is feasible or not worthy of receiving zakat funds. The results of the IDZ village of Cipancar have a score of 0.51. These results indicate that the cipancar village in the Serangpanajng sub-district, the subang is in a fairly good condition and can be considered to be considered getting zakat funds or receiving a zakat compliance behavior program. Here are the full results:

TABLE 8. THE TOTAL VALUE OF IDZ IN CIPANCAR VILLAGE, SERANGPANJANG SUB-DISTRICT

Variable	IDZ value	Information	Interpretation
Economy	0,28	Not Good	Prioritized for assistance
Health	0,32	Not Good	Prioritized for assistance
Education	0,64	Good	Less prioritized for assistance

Social and Humanity	0,70	Good	Less prioritized for assistance
Da'wah	0,65	Good	Less prioritized for assistance
Total IDZ	0,51	Good Enough	Can be considered for assistance

Source : Data processed by the researcher

From this table it can be seen that each variable has different results. Economic variables have an IDZ value of 0.28 and the health variable has an IDZ value of 0.32. These results indicate that health and economic variables have interpretations to be prioritized variables to be assisted. While the results of other variables, such as education variables of 0.64, social and humanitarian variables of 0.70, and the da'wah variable of 0.65. These results indicate that the three variables are not prioritized for assistance.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1. Conclusion

1. Zakat Village Index is an assessment tool to find out the condition of a village (economy, health, education, community social, and da'wah) whether it is worthy to receive zakat funds.
2. Cipancar Village is a village in Serangpanjang sub-district, Subang regency, West Java. This village has geographical conditions with extensive rice fields. The livelihoods of residents in Cipanjar Village are dominated as farm laborers.
3. The results of the Zakat Village Index measurement of Cipancar Village show that Cipancar Village is in a pretty good condition, which means that the village can be recommended to be given assistance in zakat funds or to receive in zakat community development programs.
4. If Cipancar Village will be given empowerment program assistance through zakat funds, both from BAZNAS and LAZ, then the aspects that need to be emphasized for program assistance are economic and health aspects. Because based on the results of IDZ calculations, the economic and health aspects of the village are in poor condition

5.2. Recommendation

1. For zakat institutions, whether it is BAZNAS or LAZ that will provide zakat funds in order to empower the cipancar village. We recommend that you focus more on economic and health variables. Because based on IDZ calculation, the two indicators are still not good.
2. To improve the economy in Cipancar Village, zakat institutions can make programs from zakat funds by building a market center. So that the products of local farmers can be directly sold by them at prices that are in line with the market. And also by making microfinance institutions from zakat funds to provide capital trading assistance for residents in Cipancar Village. In the field of Health itself, zakat funds can be used to make Public Health Centers to maintain the health of the local population.

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